

WAYS OF LEARNING ENGLISH WITH AN ASSISTANCE OF A COMPUTER AND INTERNET

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Abstract: *This article deals with the methods of acquiring English with Internet and some commonly known applications to use.*

Key words: *Internet, error-free, access, skill, download, service.*

The life of a modern person is difficult to imagine without computers and the Internet. Nowadays, almost everything is connected with computers. The computer represents one of the most amazing and significant human achievements.

The use of a computer as a tool for working with information is very diverse and multifaceted. Whatever you do - draw, write, count, play - the computer obediently executes your commands. It has a high speed, does not get tired, stores large amounts of information. The computer receives the information, processes it and outputs the result. He can look through the electronic library in a few seconds and find the required information. The computer helps you, teaches, entertains.

Many computers around the world are connected in a special way into computer networks. The Internet is the most popular. With its help, a large amount of information is transmitted, magazine articles, business letters, poems and prose, opinions and views, games and jokes, in a word, everything that can be converted into computer information and sent over communication channels. At the same time, you are guaranteed a quick and error-free exchange of information, quick access to it and its processing.

Now the Internet has great information capabilities and no less impressive services. The Internet creates a unique opportunity for foreign language learners to use texts, listen and communicate with native speakers. With the development of the Internet, the opportunities for learning English have increased significantly. Due to the fact that English is spoken in many parts of the world. The Internet space is filled with information in English, which also plays a teaching role. It is the Internet that

is considered the technical breakthrough of the last decades, which had a very strong influence on the development of educational technologies. In addition to the fact that a lot of recommendations and educational materials are posted on the Internet, the technical capabilities of the World Wide Web provide an opportunity to conduct educational classes directly on the network. On the net you can find almost all methodological materials for learning English, online tests and multimedia materials. All this is widely used in the study of English. The Internet space allows you to immediately put into practice your knowledge of the English language online. With the help of the Internet, a person can communicate with residents of various countries and representatives of various ethnic and cultural communities, thus not only improving their knowledge of the language, but also improving the skills of understanding English speech among representatives of various peoples. With the help of online communication, a person does not need to simulate a situation or a role-playing game, since he is already in live communication. Also, many English teachers recommend using the Internet to manipulate speech etiquette formulas,

We can use the Internet:

-for independent search for information as part of the work on the topic of the lesson;

- for independent study;

- for self-preparation for examinations.

In addition, during extracurricular time, you can independently work on improving your knowledge in the field of a foreign language. To do this, there are many different courses in the networks for different categories of students, designed for self-education or learning under the guidance of a teacher.

Participation in chats, in which teenagers from different countries of the world take part, is an additional, very interesting and useful opportunity for new contacts in real speech practice. So far, this type of language learning has not been sufficiently studied, but it is only a matter of time. During discussions, conversations, there is not only an exchange of information on a particular problem, but also acquaintance with some elements of another culture.

The Internet is a universal means of finding information and transferring knowledge. The indisputable advantage of the Internet is that it is an inexhaustible source of information on any issue.

I have researched several sites that can help you learn and improve your English.

The most popular sites for language learning:

1. www.busuu.com
2. Lingualeo.ru
3. abc-english-grammars
4. alleng.ru
5. <https://www.duolingo.com/>
6. <http://begin-english.ru/>
7. <http://www.learnenglish.de/>
8. <http://situationalenglish.blogspot.ru/> and others. (Attachment 1)

Thus, using the information resources of the Internet, you can achieve the following results:

- a) learn to read correctly;
- b) improve pronunciation skills;
- c) improve grammatical skills;
- d) expand your vocabulary;
- e) get acquainted with cultural knowledge, including speech etiquette,

features of the speech behavior of various peoples in the conditions of communication, cultural features, traditions of the country of the language being studied.

The rapid development of the Internet has significant costs. The modern scientific and educational information environment is characterized by a large number of educational resources with unstructured and, moreover, not always reliable information. The volume of such resources is growing exponentially. Thus, the need to ensure the effective use of information scientific and educational resources is steadily increasing.

In addition, along with useful and necessary information, users are faced with resources containing unethical and aggressive content that students can come into contact with. The uncontrolled distribution of inappropriate content is contrary to the goals of education and upbringing of young people.

It is pointless to refuse the benefits of information technology, but uncontrolled access to the Internet can lead to a number of problems:

- cyber dependencies;
- infection with malware when downloading files;
- violation of normal development.

The main harmful factors affecting the health of people working at a computer:

- sitting position for a long time;
- exposure to electromagnetic radiation of the monitor;

- eyestrain, eye strain;
- overload of the joints of the hands;
- Stress when information is lost.

Sitting position.

It would seem that a person sits at a computer in a relaxed position, but it is forced and unpleasant for the body: the neck, head muscles, arms and shoulders are tense, hence the excessive load on the spine, osteochondrosis, and scoliosis in children. In addition, a sedentary lifestyle often leads to hypertension and obesity.

Electromagnetic radiation.

Modern monitors have become safer for health, but not yet completely. And if you have a very old monitor on your desk, it's better to stay away from it.

Impact on vision.

The eyes register the smallest vibration of a text or picture, and even more so the flicker of the screen. Eye overload leads to loss of visual acuity. Poor selection of colors, fonts, layout of windows in the programs you use, and incorrect screen arrangement have a bad effect on vision.

Overloading of the joints of the hands.

The nerve endings of the fingertips seem to be broken from constant blows to the keys, numbness, weakness appear, goosebumps run in the pads. This can lead to damage to the articular and ligamentous apparatus of the hand, and in the future, hand diseases can become chronic.

Stress at information loss.

Not all users make regular backup copies of their information. But viruses do not sleep, and the hard drives of the best companies sometimes break, and the most experienced programmer can sometimes press the wrong button. As a result of such stress, heart attacks also occurred.

To improve the condition of the lungs, eyes, neck muscles and hands in between computer work, we recommend exercises borrowed from yoga. They need to be repeated 5 times. (Appendix 3)

Undoubtedly, the Internet can be used as an effective applications for the development of grammatical, lexical skills and abilities, knowledge testing. This includes all kinds of training lexical, grammar, phonetic exercises, reading tests, grammar, IQ tests, etc. Teachers or students themselves can find such sites on the WWW. In order to find out where and what development sites exist, what benefits they can bring, we have identified

the following official educational sites on the Internet, all of them are free, targeted at different users and built in different formats:

1. Duolingo is one of the most popular services for learning foreign languages from scratch. The program is built in the form of a "tree of achievements": in order to move to a new level, you must first score a certain number of points that are given for correct answers. There are apps for iOS and Android.

2. LearnEnglish - materials for learning English are collected here in different formats: lessons, games, chatting, etc. The site is available in English.

3. Situational English - offers to learn English through situations. The site contains about 150 articles, which, depending on the context, offer ready-made expressions and reactions. The materials are available in Russian.

4. Real-english.com - a site with lessons, articles and videos. Also available in Russian.

5. Learn American English online - all material is divided into levels and highlighted in a certain color for convenience. And teacher Paul explains grammar in video format.

6. Learnathome is a Russian service, convenient in that a lesson plan is formed for the student every day, which can be completed in 30 minutes. Before starting, the user is advised to take a quick test that will determine the level of knowledge of the language. If the test is skipped, the service will install the program for the elementary level.

7. Edu-station is a Russian-language site where you can not only watch video lectures, work with notes and books, but also with an interactive dictionary. There is paid content.

8. Ororo.tv is a service for learning English while watching movies and popular TV shows. The video player has a built-in translator, in which you need to select the Russian language.

9. Film-english - a site for learning language with the help of short films was created by English teacher Kieran Donahue - the winner of a number of prestigious educational awards in the UK.

10. TuneintoEnglish - The site offers to learn English through music. Here you can write down lyrics from dictation, sing karaoke, find exercises for the lyrics and guess which song it is about from the diagrams.

11. FreeRice - English vocabulary trainer with grammar exercises and tests. The service is supported by the United Nations World Food Program, so the lessons are built like a game - for every correct answer you get some rice to feed the hungry.

12. Memrise - the site is available in English. During the training, the user is offered to choose a meme for better memorization of the word or create

their own associative image. Then you need to perform exercises to choose the correct answer and the perception of the word by ear. The service is also available for iOS and Android.

13. ManyThings - the site is aimed at those who are preparing for tests or exams in English. There are sections for practicing pronunciation (American, English), idioms, slang and more.

14. Babelio - here you can read books in the original with a professional translation in front of your eyes. The books are available for free to read, but a subscription is required to access the full versions.

15. Begin-English - English for beginners. A large selection of various educational materials collected by students and graduate students of Moscow State University during volunteer ambushes.

16. Englishtips.org - All English textbooks are collected here and available for download or reading online.

In our work, the method of questioning has become the leading one. Questioning is a kind of research method of questioning in psychology and pedagogy, which allows, based on the analysis of written answers to the proposed questions, to identify points of view and trends that take place in a group of respondents (V.G. Ryndak).

In our work, we decided to explore the role of computer technology in learning a foreign language. And for this purpose, we conducted a survey, which consisted of 7 questions.

After analyzing the results of the survey, we came to the following conclusions:

- for 62% of students, a computer is a source of information;
- 73% prefer gaming computer programs;
- 46% believe that the use of computers makes learning a foreign language interesting;
- 56% of students believe that the use of computers can enrich vocabulary;
- 57% of students believe that the use of computers in the study of a foreign language contributes to better mastery of grammar; 50% of students use the Internet when teaching a foreign language;
- 92% use the Internet to find reports for foreign language lessons.

As the results of the survey showed, majority of students are computer literate. Among the students there are users of a fairly good level. This means that the children can not only masterfully play various computer games, but also have the skills to work in various computer programs, communicate on the Internet, and create computer presentations for lessons and events.

CONCLUSION

The study showed that the use of computer technology is not only a source of pleasure, but first of all, it is a way of obtaining information. Many have the skills to work in various computer programs, create computer presentations, communicate on the Internet.

We have compiled an analysis of educational Internet sites. By teaching authentic language, the Internet helps build conversational skills, as well as teaching vocabulary and grammar, providing genuine interest and therefore efficiency. Moreover, the Internet develops skills that are important not only for a foreign language. This is primarily associated with mental operations: analysis, synthesis, abstraction, comparison, comparison, verbal and semantic forecasting, etc. Thus, the skills and abilities formed with the help of Internet technologies go beyond the limits of foreign language competence even within the framework of the “language” aspect. The Internet develops the social and psychological qualities of students: their self-confidence and their ability to work in a team; creates an environment conducive to learning,

The hypothesis is conclusive and appropriate: “If the Internet has a good effect on the learning process of students, then it can be introduced into the curriculum, ultimately this will speed up the learning process,” but in no case will it replace live communication between a teacher and a student.

In this age of high technology, computers play a huge role in learning English, as there is an interesting and useful opportunity for new ways of gaining knowledge. Thus, we came to the conclusion that the Internet can really help and speed up the process of learning a foreign language.

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